

Navigation in Dental Implants –A Review

Dr.Khushee Vishnu Agrawal¹, Dr.Prashanth Raghuram Shetty², Dr.Deepthi Prashanth Shetty³,

Dr.Yogita Fakira Kshirsagar⁴, Dr.Mahendra Babanrao Ghodge⁵, Dr.Sakshi Suresh Aglawe⁶

^{1,6}*Post graduate student, Department of Periodontology, Yogita Dental College and Hospital, Khed, Ratnagiri, Maharashtra- 415709*

²*Professor, Department of Periodontology, Yogita Dental College and Hospital, Khed, Ratnagiri, Maharashtra- 415709*

³*Professor, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, SDM College of Dental Sciences and Hospital, Shri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwara University, Dharwad, Karnataka 580009.*

⁴*PhD student, Department of Periodontology, Government Dental College and Hospital, Mumbai, Maharashtra 400001.*

⁵*Post graduate student, Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Yogita Dental College and Hospital, Khed, Ratnagiri, Maharashtra- 415709.*

Corresponding Author- Dr.Prashanth Shetty, Professor, Yogita Dental College & Hospital,

Naringi Riverside, At Post Tal Dist. SH104, Khed, Maharashtra 415709.

Name	Phone number	Email
Dr.Khushee Vishnu Agrawal	+919833441360	khushee12@gmail.com
Dr.Prashanth Raghuram Shetty	+919886191999	drprashanthshetty3@gmail.com
Dr.Deepthi Prashanth Shetty	+918105307631	kdepthishetty@gmail.com
Dr.Yogita Fakira Kshirsagar	+918928930921	yoksh.yk.yk@gmail.com
Dr.Mahendra Babanrao Ghodge	+917058428948	ghodgemahendra@gmail.com
Dr.Sakshi Suresh Aglawe	+917558542763	aglawesakshi55@gmail.com

Received: Mar 25, 2026

Accepted: Apr 08, 2026

Published: Apr 10, 2026

Abstract

Implants is one of the most predictable and well established treatment modality for the replacement of missing teeth. Computer assisted implant surgery is a recently developed technique for placement of dental implants. Navigation systems used for the placement of dental implants enhances the predictability and accuracy of the implant placement. Potential Intraoperative and post-operative complications are reduced, thereby reducing patient morbidity. There are two types of computer assisted implant surgeries, static CAIS which utilizes surgical guides for placement of implants and dynamic CAIS which is based on the motion tracking technology and enables real time tracking of implants.

Key Words- Navigation in implants, Dynamic Navigation, Static Navigation, Computer assisted implant surgery, Dental implants

1. Introduction

The discovery of X-rays by W. C. Roentgen has revolutionized the world of medicine and dentistry. The advent of CBCT, intraoral scanners, face scanners, CAD CAM milling units, and 3D printers has led to major breakthroughs in implant dentistry, significantly contributing to novel treatment modalities and treatment planning [2]. Implants have become a well-established treatment modality for the rehabilitation of fully or partially edentulous arches. [10] Computer-assisted implant surgery (CAIS) is one such treatment modality recently developed to reduce alterations to essentially pre-planned implant placement processes in dental implantology. [13]. Navigation in implants permits the dentist to position the dental implant in the optimal way to get the finest prosthetically driven outcomes and enhance aesthetics [13]. Precise positioning of implants is crucial for favorable prosthetic outcomes, long-term success, and stability of the soft and hard tissues surrounding implants. Accurate positioning of implants enables optimum design and fabrication of superstructures, contributing to the long-term success of dental implants.

2. Types of Computer-Assisted Implant Surgery

There are two types of CAIS: static and dynamic.

Static Computer-Assisted Implant Surgeries utilize 3D-printed surgical guides and a special drilling set. Custom-made tools called static guides are created from a three-dimensional representation of the patient's anatomy. The guides serve as a pattern for the surgeon to follow when placing implants by fitting over the patient's jaw bones. X-ray imaging is usually employed with the guides to ensure precise implant placement.

Advantages of Static CAIS:

1. It reduces post-operative morbidity by enabling flapless or limited flap elevation.[14]
2. Compared to freehand methods, it offers precise implant spacing and angulation.[14]
3. Appropriate implant angulation and depth for aesthetic scenarios can be ensured with virtual implant planning and guided insertion. [14]

Disadvantages of Static CAIS:

1. Because the stent is static, no plan modifications can be made, consequently the surgery might have to be repeated if the static guide does not seat precisely on the teeth or tissues. Also, intraoperative surgical plans cannot be altered in real time.[14]
2. Fabricating preoperative guide plates takes time and incurs costs.
3. Static guides present challenges when placement is needed in the second molar regions, and the patient has limited mouth opening.
4. Specific implant surgical tools are required.
5. The ability to irrigate the drill is limited when using CT-generated guide stents throughout the procedure due to restricted access to the bone and the possibility of higher heat production.[14]

Different methods can be used to create a drill guide. Some guides are produced through rapid prototyping, while others are created using mechanical positioning devices that transform a prosthesis based on a radiographic scan into a surgical guide (Fortin et al., 2002, 2004).[20]

Static navigation can be categorized into full-guided (FG) and half-guided (HG) implant surgeries. Additionally, static navigation can be classified based on the type of surgical guide stents into:

Open and closed guided stents, or

Mucosa-supported, bone-supported, and tooth-crown-supported guided stents.

Three factors can be used to categorise static navigation surgery:

- I. Guide support type;
- II. Surgical visibility type; and
- III. Drilling and implant placement facility type.

1. GUIDESUPPORT

a) MUCOSA-SUPPORTED GUIDE-

Flapless surgery is associated with the use of surgical guides supported by the oral mucosa. In patients who are partially or completely edentulous, a mucosa-supported guide should be the primary option if the bone architecture allows for the flapless technique. The palatal mucosa, along with the buccal and lingual mucosal flanges, support surgical templates in people who are completely edentulous. In partially edentulous individuals, a combination of mucosa- and tooth/crown-supported guides improves surgical template stability. Additionally, in fully dentate patients, trans-mucosal fixation pins are often employed to further improve the stability of the surgical template.

b) BONE-SUPPORTED GUIDE-

The bone surface supports the surgical guide in a manner that requires a full-thickness flap's reflection. This approach is recommended in cases involving bone deficiencies, anatomical constraints, or when bone augmentation procedures are necessary.

c) TOOTH/CROWN SUPPORTED GUIDE-

In partially edentulous patients, the remaining teeth or crowns are used to enhance the stability of surgical guide templates. Bone and mucosal support can also be applied simultaneously when appropriate. In completely edentulous patients, transitional implants may serve as an additional strategy to improve surgical guide stabilization.

2. SURGICAL FIELD VISIBILITY TYPE

a. CLOSED GUIDES

During bone drilling and implant placement, closed guide stents fully enclose the operative field, preventing direct visualization of the mucosa or bone. They are most commonly used in fully guided surgeries and are more restrictive compared to open guide stents.

b. OPEN GUIDES

Open guide templates feature buccal-side access, allowing a clear buccal view of the surgical field which allows for direct visual control over the bone and mucosa during the bone drilling procedure and implant placement.

3. DRILLING AND IMPLANT PLACEMENT

a. FULL-GUIDED (FG)

This approach is also referred to as computer-directed surgery or guided surgery. To perform guided implant placement using fully guided static navigation, CBCT imaging, 3D planning, and prosthetic analysis must be completed prior to the fabrication of a computer-generated surgical template. The overall surgical procedure—including bone drilling and implant placement—is directed by this computer-designed stent. Fully guided surgery is often performed flaplessly, because computer-guided templates and 3D design offer enough information to do away with the necessity for flap elevation.. However, successful flapless surgery requires adequate keratinized mucosa and bone volume to avoid the need for regenerative procedures. In cases where there is insufficient bone or keratinized tissue, flap surgery is strongly recommended in conjunction with fully guided implant placement. This approach allows for bone regeneration procedures and helps preserve the maximum amount of keratinized mucosa by avoiding punch incisions.

b. HALF-GUIDED (HG)

Also referred to as partial-guided surgery, this method may involve preoperative planning and prosthetic evaluation using a three-dimensional cast model alongside 3D CBCT imaging. While 2D radiographic imaging can be used, 3D radiological planning is strongly recommended for greater accuracy. A surgical stent—whether computer-fabricated or not—can be utilized in one of three ways: non-computer-guided, drilling-guided, or pilot-drill-guided approaches.

HALF GUIDED can be further classified into

i. DRILLING GUIDED-

Every bone drilling sequence uses a surgical guide. The surgical guide is removed once the implant is inserted.

ii. PILOT-DRILL GUIDED-

This method is also known as first-drill guided surgery. In this approach, the surgical guide is used solely for the pilot drilling phase of the bone preparation sequence. After the pilot drill is completed, the guide is removed, and the remaining surgical steps are performed freehand.

iii. NON-COMPUTER GUIDED

In this approach, surgical templates that are not computer-fabricated are used to guide both implant placement and the bone drilling process. These stents are developed through 3D planning, which involves cast-model analysis combined with CBCT or conventional radiographic (XR) imaging. Typically, a thermoplastic radiographic stent is fabricated using a diagnostic wax-up or a temporary prosthesis as a reference. This radiographic stent is then converted into a surgical guide.

4. FREE-HAND GUIDED

Also known as mental-guided, brain-guided, or traditional surgery, this approach relies entirely on the surgeon's clinical judgment and experience. Pre-surgical planning may or may not include CBCT imaging, although 3D planning is strongly recommended. No surgical templates are used during the bone drilling or implant placement stages

5. DYNAMIC COMPUTER-ASSISTED IMPLANT SURGERIES [1]

They are based on motion-tracking technology, which enables real-time tracking of the dental drill and patient during the procedure. Optical systems track the patient and the handpiece, displaying images on a monitor. Dynamic navigation systems provide real-time drilling and

placement guidance/feedback by tracking the position of the implant drill tip and mapping it to a previously obtained CBCT scan of the patient's jaw.

The three crucial procedures that enable Drill tip mapping in real time to the intended CBCT image volume of the patient are registration, calibration, and tracking. The system provides a "cross-hair" or "bull's-eye" display when the drill gets close to a pre-planned implant location, aiding the surgeon in precisely navigating to the planned drill entry point, adjusting the drill orientation, and navigating the osteotomy site to the planned depth. Optical systems use either an active or passive tracking array.[11]

1. Active Tracking:[14]Stereo cameras track infrared light emitted by active tracking system arrays.

2. Passive Tracking:[14]in which Reflecting spheres are used to bounce infrared light back to the stereo camera from a light source.

Tracking arrays, also known as passive patterned arrays, are attached to both the surgical instruments and the patient's jaw. These arrays reflect light, which is captured by two stereo cameras positioned above the patient. The reflected light allows the Dynamic Navigation (DN) system to determine the real-time positions of both the patient and the instruments in relation to the pre-surgical plan. This process occurs dynamically, enabling continuous tracking during the procedure. A virtual image is displayed for the surgical team, allowing the surgeon to perform the implant procedure with the aid of this virtual reality system. The surgical plan might also be changed at any time by the surgeon based on the current clinical situation.[7]

There are separate fiducials for dentate and edentulous patients

In dentate patients, the fiducial clip must be securely placed on a tooth and consistently repositioned in the exact same location. It is critical that the clip is firmly seated during the CBCT scan to ensure accurate data acquisition. The clip features a tracker arm, which should be oriented buccally—towards the patient's cheek. Its placement must not interfere with the implant placement or drilling procedures, even when located on the same arch as the implant site. Additionally, it should not obstruct the surgeon's visual field or hinder the assistant's access and use of instruments.

Mobile teeth, pontics on bridges, or teeth with orthodontic wires should be avoided as placement sites. The thermoplastic material on the fiducial clip is softened by immersing it in a hot water bath (60°C – 71°C) for approximately 3 to 5 minutes until it turns clear, indicating readiness for use. The clip is then positioned on at least three teeth—ideally spaced equally from the buccal and lingual sides—with the tracker arm oriented buccally. It should remain in place for at least one minute to allow the material to cool to a surface temperature below 40°C.

Proper fit is confirmed by applying vertical pressure until no further movement is possible, indicating a secure seating. The clip is then carefully removed and placed in a cold water bath, avoiding any rocking motion that might distort its shape. The fit is rechecked by repositioning the clip to ensure it remains accurate, stable, and does not impinge on soft tissues. In cases requiring dual fiducial clips, they must be placed independently, with no physical contact between them.

In edentulous patients, fiducial markers—typically small screws—must be inserted into the patient's bone to enable accurate navigation. These fiducials can be placed either directly into exposed bone by raising a flap or through the soft tissue using small stab incisions apical to the mucogingival junction. Precise planning and careful placement of these fiducials are essential to avoid complications.

These fiducials also serve a critical role during the preoperative phase, as they are used for registration with the navigation software. To prevent injury to anatomical structures such as the inferior alveolar nerve, short screws measuring 4 mm or 5 mm in length and 1.5 mm in diameter are used. If vertical bone reduction is planned, it is necessary to position the fiducials apically to the desired bone reduction area to maintain their stability and accuracy.

Additionally, care must be taken to avoid injury to the infraorbital and inferior alveolar nerves during placement. A minimum of four fiducials should be placed, distributed evenly across the arch to ensure stability and to accommodate the attachment of the edentulous fiducial plate during the surgical procedure.

Parts of Dynamic Navigation System:[6]

1. A computer that runs the navigation software and shows the drill location on the CBCT images.
2. A camera that records the tracking arrays placed on the patient and the surgical handpiece.

Advantages of Dynamic CAIS:[11]

1. Implant surgeons can assess, scan, plan, and execute implant surgery on the same day without waiting for the creation of a static surgical guide stent or incurring additional costs.
2. Alterations in the implant's placement, system, and size intraoperatively can be incorporated when clinical circumstances demand it.
3. Dynamic navigation helps minimize patient trauma by avoiding the need to open a flap and giving surgeons confidence in proper implant placement.

4. The system allows surgeons to evaluate accuracy at every stage of the procedure.
5. Dynamic navigation is statistically more exact and accurate than freehand placement.
6. Ergonomically, it reduces the need for the surgeon to bend their neck or back for extended periods, enabling them to focus more intently on the screen.
7. It permits guidance of implant placement in situations where interdental spaces make it impossible to use suitable guidance tubes with static guides.

Disadvantages of Dynamic CAIS:[11]

1. Steep learning curve and the need for operator training.
2. Heavy handpiece and the challenge of achieving hand-eye coordination without continued practice.
3. The operating surgeon must have expert skills in haptic feedback.
4. The surgeon should be able to perform the entire procedure by looking at the screen rather than the patient's mouth.

6. HYBRID NAVIGATION TECHNIQUE[12]

Static guides create a hybrid technique that incorporates the advantages of both static and dynamic technologies when used with dynamic navigation. The dynamic navigation system provides real-time feedback and guidance to ensure proper implant placement, while the static guide offers the surgeon a physical blueprint to follow during the process. The positioning and stabilization of stents throughout each phase of treatment is one of the most delicate and critical aspects of the procedure. Precise placement of every stent is essential; therefore, establishing and consistently maintaining an accurate maxillomandibular relationship record from the outset is imperative.

Following the registration and calibration of the fiducial markers, an accuracy check must be performed to ensure the correct positioning of the surgical stent. This step is vital for the reliability of the guided surgery.[23]

During the procedure, once the static guide is securely affixed to the bone, the surgeon uses the Dynamic Navigation (DN) system to guide the precise placement of the implant, enhancing surgical accuracy and predictability. By giving the surgeon feedback in real-time, the dynamic

navigation system enables them to modify the implant's position as necessary. Combining static guides with dynamic navigation can increase implant placement accuracy and precision, especially in more complex surgeries. This sophisticated surgical method has several advantages for both surgeons and patients.

Rolf Ewers et al. (2004)[30] published an extensive study summarizing seven years of research, development, and clinical application of computer-aided navigation technology in dental implantology. Initially, general-purpose navigation software was adapted for implantology, and by 2001, a specialized software module tailored to dental implantology became available. Preoperative planning was conducted with a focus on prosthetic requirements.

In routine clinical practice, optoelectronic tracking systems were used to register intraoperative patient and drill positions, while electromagnetic trackers were evaluated in preclinical settings. Over the seven-year period (1995–2002), no complications were reported, and surgical execution closely matched the preoperative plans.

The introduction of dental implantology-specific clinical software reduced the preparation time for navigated surgical procedures from two to three days to approximately one and a half days. The use of computer-aided navigation significantly improved treatment quality, enhanced intraoperative safety, and allowed for precise fulfillment of preoperative plans by minimizing risks to adjacent teeth and nerves.

. George A. Mandelaris et al. (2018)[1] published a case report of a 29-year-old female patient with gastroesophageal reflux disorder (GERD), migraines, narcolepsy, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), and depression. Two implants were placed after immediate extraction of teeth 11 and 21, along with placement of bone graft material using the dynamic navigation technique. The accuracy results showed implant apex depth deviations of 1.10 mm and 1.37 mm, entry point deviations of 0.13 mm and 0.41 mm, and angle discrepancies of 4.3 degrees and 6.76 degrees for teeth 11 and 21, respectively. Osseointegration was verified after three months, and the final prosthetic stage was completed after six months.

Dong Wu et al. (2020)[3] compared the accuracy of dynamic navigation (DN) with a static surgical guide (SSG) for dental implant placement. 38 implants were subjected to dynamic navigation, and 57 implants were subjected to static surgical guidance. The study concluded that dynamic navigation could achieve accurate implant placement similar to the static surgical guide. The accuracy of dynamic navigation was not influenced by the experience level of the surgeon or implant site and seemed higher than the static surgical guide in molar regions.

Gerardo Pellegrino et al. (2021)[6] conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis of 32 studies, demonstrating that dynamic navigation resulted in implant placement deviations comparable in magnitude to those seen with static computer-guided surgery. However, when

compared to conventional freehand surgery, dynamic navigation proved to be significantly more precise, indicating its superiority for achieving accurate implant placement.

In a 2022 study, Xiaotong Wang et al.[28] assessed the performance of both novice and experienced clinicians in performing osteotomies and implant insertions using three different approaches: freehand, static surgical guides, and dynamic navigation. Regardless of operator expertise, the results demonstrated that dynamic navigation greatly decreased angular deviation as compared to both freehand and static-guided approaches. Although the navigation approach required more time than freehand procedures, experienced practitioners were still able to complete the surgeries faster than novices. Notably, novice clinicians reported higher self-confidence levels when using guided approaches, and their confidence with dynamic navigation was comparable to that of experienced practitioners. The study concluded that dynamic navigation is a valuable tool in dental implantology, enabling less experienced clinicians to achieve accuracy and confidence levels similar to those of seasoned professionals—an advantage not observed with freehand or static-guided techniques.

Pragati Nirula et al. (2023)[b] performed surgery on 60 patients using dynamic navigation and freehand implant placement techniques, assessing patient satisfaction through a questionnaire. The study found that patients were more interested in the future of robotics in dentistry due to visualizing the procedure and understanding the implant placement. Patients welcomed the improved comfort and reduced immediate post-operative pain with dynamic navigation.

Mathew Mampilly et al. (2023)[29] conducted an in vitro study aimed at comparing the accuracy of implant placement using a dynamic navigation system versus freehand drilling, among practitioners with varying levels of experience. The study assessed surgical precision, procedural duration, and surgeons' self-confidence. Findings indicated that, irrespective of experience level, the dynamic navigation system consistently enabled more accurate implant placement than the freehand method. Notably, novice practitioners benefited the most, as the system significantly reduced their placement deviations, allowing them to achieve results comparable to those of experienced clinicians.

In a separate in vitro study, Caroline Carrico et al. (2024)[25] evaluated the skill progression of novice operators in freehand implant placement. Senior dental students with no prior implant experience were tasked with placing two implants supporting a three-unit fixed prosthesis on a simulated model. After initial freehand attempts, they were exposed to static guides, dynamic navigation, and template-based guide techniques. The aim was to assess whether experience with guided methods influenced their subsequent freehand performance. The study found that guided placement did not significantly improve or impair freehand skills within the scope of the pilot trial. The authors emphasized the importance of exposing dental students to a range of implant placement techniques to prepare them for clinical decision-making and to enable them to choose the most appropriate method based on their skills and the clinical context.

Moreover, numerous investigations have demonstrated that the freehand approach is a leading cause of deviations from surgical plans, often resulting in prosthetic compromises and posing significant risks to surgical safety.

7. Conclusion

The shift from analogue 2D imaging and diagnostics to digital 3D technologies has significantly deepened our understanding of the complexities involved in implant surgery and prosthetic rehabilitation. This natural evolution in diagnostic tools has enhanced the precision and predictability of treatment planning and execution.[7]

The advancement of Dynamic Navigation (DN) technology, combined with pre-operative 3D planning, now enables clinicians to approach implant cases with greater accuracy and confidence. This translates into improved patient outcomes and more predictable prognoses.[6]

From a cost-benefit perspective, static template systems are more affordable and easier to manufacture, whereas dynamic navigation systems entail higher initial investment and operational costs. Nevertheless, the precision, adaptability, and enhanced visualization offered by dynamic systems provide compelling clinical advantages.[16]

Digital technology in implantology continues to evolve rapidly, paving the way for ongoing improvements in accuracy, usability, and therapeutic potential. While dynamic navigation systems already offer substantial benefits over static guides, particularly in terms of flexibility and intraoperative feedback, further innovation is needed to address cost-efficiency and ease of use.[24]

In summary, computer-aided navigation stands out as a promising and effective tool in dental implantology, with proven benefits in enhancing intraoperative safety, surgical accuracy, and overall treatment quality.[30]

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